

Impacts of economic emerging trends on supply chain resilience – a literature review

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Purpose

The latest years have been marked by major events that have affected global supply chains: e.g., the pandemic, the semi-conductor crisis, the war in Ukraine and recently the conflict between Israel and Palestine. These events have resulted into several types of supply chain disruptions, e.g., shipment delays, lack of supplies and related commodities prices increments, rationing, congestions in ports, stockouts, bullwhip effects etc. (WEF, 2022a) The impacts on global trade have been enormous, and therefore governments are intensifying and diversifying investments in order to re-shore supplies locally or in “friendly” countries (friend shoring) (Maihold, 2022, Choudhary et al., 2023, WEF, 2022b). Likewise, several companies have initiated internal programs to ensure the resilience of their global operations. However, there is uncertainty regarding the risks to anticipate and their potential impact on operations. Hence, the purpose of this paper is to identify most significant economic megatrends, and related supply chain risks with a medium long-term horizon (2030-2050).

Design/methodology/approach

To incorporate the latest trends and account for unexpected disruptions such as the pandemic or the Ukraine war, a thorough analysis of literature was conducted. The goal was to gain insight into the megatrends and trends that could impact manufacturing, process manufacturing, logistics, and supply chain management. Additionally, the literature review was supplemented by insights gathered from external stakeholders during a workshop.

Findings

The analysis performed in this work has settle two megatrends: the global trade shift and the digital economy (Figure 1). The global trade shift has undergone significant changes in recent years, including the emergence of rising inflation and transportation costs. The long-standing pattern of globalization has also been significantly reorganized. Factors such as the aftermath of the Covid-19 crisis and the ongoing conflict in Ukraine, among others, have played a pivotal role in slowing down export growth (which is now in recovery). These factors have impacted the economic expansion in emerging countries and reshaped investment flows in the recent period. The digitalization megatrend continues to flourish,

evident in the growing adoption of digital platforms, digital payments facilitated by financial technologies, and the surge in the sharing economy.

Figure 1. Megatrends and trends affecting risks to supply chains.

When assessing the risks associated with the global trade shift, several significant challenges emerge. Capacity constraints and supply chain shortages have exerted a considerable impact on supply chains in recent years, posing a major obstacle. Additionally, changes in consumption patterns and purchasing partners, coupled with a decline in customer trust, have led to societal shifts. In terms of the digital economy, security concerns pose the most pressing risks that need to be addressed to ensure a successful implementation. The issue of data sharing required for certain digital applications further highlights the lack of integration and collaboration among supply chain stakeholders. Lastly, the rapid evolution of digitalization within the market presents a challenge for companies to adapt quickly, potentially putting them at a disadvantage compared to more agile competitors.

Relevance/Contribution

Supply chain resilience is the capability of supply chains to bounce back to original conditions or new states after a disruption (Christopher and Peck, 2004). Ivanov (2023) distinguish two views of resilience: the Stability Based View (SBV), which concern the response of the supply chain to recover and return to its initial view. Next, the Adaptation Based View (ABV), which concerns the ability to survive and adapt to a new context in a manner to ensure performance. Several authors agree that supply chain resilience is highly dependent on the capacity of being pro-active to risks (Ivanov, 2023, Elluru et al., 2019, Shishodia et al., 2023) and therefore the capability of understanding how emerging trends and risks will impact supply chains. Previous research has investigated and identified risk elements that may affect supply chains (Shishodia et al., 2023, Betto et al., 2023). Among those the economic and natural environments in which business operates or where assets and infrastructures are located are indicated as an important source of vulnerability (Peck, 2005). Yet, none of the existing and recent studies focus on the economic dimension. Hence, an improved knowledge about evolving trends may support organization and governments with

several actions. Companies can enhance organization preparedness against upcoming risks, rethink assets capacity, re-shore operations when and where necessary, reallocate and reposition inventories, divert investments on factory or storage assets etc. Likewise, governments can support the business with trading regulations, international or regional pacts to create corridors, or regional clusters aiming to localize and incentivize production (Urciuoli et al., 2014, WEF, 2022b).

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